

Studies in the Anthraquinone Series. Synthesis of Anthraquinones related to Morindone and Emodin.

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In a recent communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 769) it has been shown by Mitter and Biswas that anthraquinone derivatives occurring in plants could be classified under four types, *viz.*, the chayroot, madder, morindone and emodin types. In the case of the chayroot and the madder types it has been further shown that the anthraquinones actually form links in oxidation and reduction chains of which the β -monosubstituted or the $\beta\beta'$ -disubstituted products are the first members.

It appeared to us to be of interest to enquire whether the hetero-nuclear anthraquinones belonging to the morindone and emodin types could also be constituted into similar oxidation and reduction chains and we thought of studying in this connection 2-hydroxy-6-methyl- and 3-hydroxy-6-methylanthraquinones (I and II) and also 1-hydroxy-6-methylanthraquinone (III), which might be regarded as possible starting points for such chains.

The first of these groupings is present in morindone, the second in emodin while the third contains a grouping which is common to both these types.

The methods of oxidation which we proposed to employ for realising the links in the oxidation series were, besides direct oxidation, indirect methods of oxidation, namely, over the nitro-derivatives.

The syntheses of 2-hydroxy-6-methyl- and 3-hydroxy 6-methyl-anthraquinones were attempted according to the following scheme.—

Similarly from (V) by an identical series of reactions, we hoped to get 3-hydroxy-6-methylanthraquinone (II).

It was found however that the condensation of 4-nitrophthalic anhydride with toluene leads to the formation of only one nitrotoluylbenzoic acid to which must be ascribed the constitution (IV) as

the unthraquinone (I) obtained from it gave on alkali fusion a product (VIII) which is identical with the anthraquinone prepared by Mitter and Biswas (*loc. cit.*) by condensing hemipinic anhydride with toluene and to which the formula (VIII) has been ascribed by the authors.

The mother-liquor after the crystallisation of the above nitrotoluoylbenzoic acid contained a small quantity of a substance having a lower melting point (not sharp) which was not further investigated.

Quite in keeping with our expectations, a dinitro-compound was formed by nitrating the anthraquinone (I) after methylation. This however after replacement of the nitro-groups by methoxyl groups by the method of Kaufer (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 65) yielded, on de-methylation, a compound which though resembling morindone in having an orange colour, being crystallisable from toluene and in giving a violet coloration with alkalis resembling that of alizarin, melted between 240° and 245° whereas pure morindone melts at 271-72°. The quantity of the substance at our disposal being small, it could not be further investigated.

As regards 1-hydroxy-6-methylanthraquinone, we attempted its synthesis by condensing 3-nitrophthalic anhydride with toluene which was expected to give us two nitrotoluoylbenzoic acids leading ultimately to the synthesis of 1-hydroxy-6-methyl and 1-hydroxy-7-methylanthraquinone.

The condensation in this case gave rise, however, to only one product.

An indirect evidence of its constitution was furnished by the fact that the hydroxytoluoylbenzoic acid obtained from it did not give any colour reaction with alcoholic ferric chloride thus pointing to its possessing the structure (XII),

(XII)

(XIII)

rather than (XIII) in which the hydroxyl group would lie adjacent to the carboxyl group.

It follows therefore that the anthraquinone derived from it must have the formula (III). Attempts at conversion of (III) into (VIII) by alkali fusion failed.

The nitration of (III) gave rise to a trinitro-derivative which is probably

judging from its analogy with chrysophanic acid.

The condensation of 3- and 4-nitrophthalic anhydrides with toluene has been previously attempted by Lawrence (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 2577) who claims to have obtained two products in each case and describes them as "brownish [amorphous powders which do not have sharp melting points and decompose on melting and while somewhat more soluble in cold than in hot alcohols they do not crystallise from these solvents."

As already mentioned, the condensation product in the case of the 4-nitrophthalic anhydride consisted *mainly* of one compound (and this is the only fact in agreement with the statements of Lawrence) while in the case of the 3-nitrophthalic anhydride exclusively one compound was formed. Again none of the statements quoted above conform to the results obtained by us.

The nitrotoluoylbenzoic acid (IV) crystallised from dilute acetic acid in small white crystals melting sharply at 171°. The nitrotoluoylbenzoic acid (IX) crystallised from dilute alcohol in glistening pale yellow scales melting sharply at 219°. We have looked for its isomer in the mother-liquors with negative results. Moreover the melting points of our compounds do not agree with those given by Lawrence for his toluoylbenzoic acids, which were evidently impure tarry products.

A very singular fact has come to light in connection with the 4-nitrophthalic anhydride condensation. As usual, the condensation was attempted in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. Every time however the experiment failed, the whole reaction mixture being converted into a tarry mass. The effect of temperature was studied and it was found that even with ice-cooling the result did not improve. Regulation of the quantity of aluminium chloride similarly proved to be ineffective. It then somehow occurred to us that our aluminium chloride was in some inexplicable way acting prejudicially in the reaction and as we had been employing fresh specimens all along we thought of moderating the reaction by the use of old specimens tempered by partial absorption of moisture from the atmosphere. To our surprise, the reaction this time proceeded smoothly and we could isolate the product in quite pure condition, the formation of tar being almost nil. In all our subsequent operations we used this partially hydrated aluminium chloride with uniform success. That the presence of moisture was the determining factor in the success of the condensation has been definitely proved by direct addition of a few drops of water to the reaction mixture in cases where formation of tar seemed inevitable (by noting the change from the normal green to the brown-red coloration of tar) owing evidently to the fact that the aluminium chloride used was not sufficiently hydrated. In all such cases the usual green colour was restored and the condensation proceeded smoothly.

As regards the 3-nitrophthalic anhydride condensation, Lawrence used the temperature of the boiling water-bath. By conducting the experiment at that temperature we have found that the formation of tar is very large so that the product presents the appearance of a 'brownish amorphous substance' the purification of which could not obviously be effected by the author. After several trial experiments the optimum temperature was found to lie between 40° and 45° at which tar formation was considerably diminished and the

product consisted of a brown plastic mass, much easier of purification.

Then, the method of purification employed by Lawrence is evidently unsatisfactory. Though he admits that he could not crystallise the substances and effected a "somewhat unsatisfactory separation" of the supposed isomers in each case, by methyl alcohol he did not apparently adopt any special means of purification for his toluoylbenzoic acids. We have on the other hand found it essential to go through a course of tedious purifying operations (specially in the case of the product from 3-nitrophthalic anhydride) before we could obtain the substances in a crystallisable condition. Of these, extraction by boiling with excess of calcium carbonate constitutes an important step, by far the greatest amount of purification being attained here.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of 3- and 4-Nitrophthalic Acids.—These were prepared by the method of Lawrence (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 1871). Phthalic acid was nitrated with fuming nitric acid when a mixture of 3- and 4-nitrophthalic acids was obtained. These were separated by the method of Miller (*Ber.*, 1878, **11**, 393). The 4-nitrophthalic acid thus obtained melted at 159-61° and was almost pure.

Preparation of 4-Nitrophthalic Anhydride.—This was prepared by the method of Bogert and Boroschek (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, **23**, 748) with some modification. 4-Nitrophthalic acid was heated in a stout distilling flask, to 190-95° in vacuum, until frothing ceased and a clear melt was obtained. This was poured out and refluxed with acetyl chloride while still in a semi-solid condition. The solution deposited crystals of 4-nitrophthalic anhydride on cooling, m.p. 112-14°. (The pure substance melts at 114°).

3-Nitro-2-p-toluoylbenzoic Acid.—3-Nitrophthalic anhydride (7.5 g.) prepared according to the method of Eder and Widmer (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922 **5**, 10) was suspended in toluene (100 c.c.) and to this aluminium chloride (15 g.) was added in small portions at a time and then the flask was heated on a water-bath at 40-50° for 5 hours. The contents of the flask were then acidified with 10% hydrochloric acid (135 c.c.) and the excess of toluene distilled off by passing in steam. The crude toluoylbenzoic acid was extracted by

hot sodium carbonate solution (100 c.c. of 10%). On acidifying with hydrochloric acid (10%) a plastic mass was obtained which was dissolved in hot acetic acid, boiled with the addition of a little animal charcoal and filtered. On dilution with water a greenish precipitate was obtained contaminated with tarry matter which was boiled with calcium carbonate and filtered. On acidifying the filtrate a light yellow precipitate of the toluoylbenzoic acid (IX) was formed. Crystallised from dilute alcohol 3.5 g. of the acid, m.p. 218-19°, were obtained as pale yellow crystalline plates. (Found: N, 5.06. $C_{15}H_{11}O_5N$ requires N, 4.91 per cent.).

3-Amino-2-p-toluoylbenzoic Acid.—Ferrous sulphate (32 g.) was dissolved in water (210 c.c.) in a wide mouthed flask, boiled and concentrated ammonia (50 c.c.) then added. To the precipitated ferrous hydroxide a warm solution of the nitrotoluoylbenzoic acid (4.5 g.) in concentrated ammonia (45 c.c.) was added, heated for 15 minutes and filtered. The filtrate was boiled to drive off ammonia. To the boiling solution a hot solution of alum (4.5 g.) in water (45 c.c.) was gradually added and the whole filtered hot, when yellow prismatic crystals of the aminotoluoylbenzoic acid (2 g.) were obtained. Recrystallised from water it melted at 165°. (Found: N, 5.81. $C_{15}H_{13}O_5N$ requires N, 5.49 per cent.).

3-Hydroxy-2-p-toluoylbenzoic Acid.—The amino-acid (2 g.) was dissolved in dilute ammonia by warming and dilute hydrochloric acid added until the precipitate first formed dissolved away. The bright yellow solution of the hydrochloride was cooled to 0° and the calculated quantity of a solution of sodium nitrite (0.6 g.) in water (7 c.c.) gradually added while stirring the mixture by a mechanical stirrer. The precipitated diazonium salt was decomposed by boiling for 15-20 minutes, a little animal charcoal added and the whole filtered hot, when silky yellow needles of the hydroxy acid (1.5 g.) were obtained. Recrystallised from ethyl acetate and petroleum ether it melted at 225-26°. It does not give any coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 70.43; H, 4.55. $C_{15}H_{13}O_4$ required C, 70.81; H, 4.69 per cent.).

1-Hydroxy-6-methylanthraquinone.—To the hydroxytoluoylbenzoic acid (2 g.) was added boric anhydride (2 g.) and sulphuric acid (4 g., *d* 1.84). To the mixture was then added fuming sulphuric acid (20 g., 20% SO_3) and heated on the water-bath for 3 hours. This was then poured into ice when an orange mass was obtained, which was extracted first with boiling water to remove boric acid

and then with a cold 5% solution of sodium carbonate. The crude anthraquinone on crystallisation from glacial acetic acid gave bright yellow needles melting at 147°. (Found: C, 75.4; H, 4.2. $C_{15}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 75.68; H, 4.2 per cent.).

The acetyl derivative crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 172°. The anthraquinone obtained on de-acetylation melted at 147°. (Found: C, 72.71; H, 4.38. $C_{17}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 72.86; H, 4.29 per cent.).

2:4:5(?)—*Trinitro-1-hydroxy-6-methylanthraquinone*.—1-Hydroxy-6-methylanthraquinone (0.5 g.) was intimately mixed with potassium nitrate (0.5 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (8 g.) added. The mixture was then heated on a water-bath for 5 hours. The nitro-compound after washing with hot water crystallised from glacial acetic acid, in tiny, golden yellow crystals, m.p. 285-86°. (Found: N, 11.39. $C_{15}H_7O_9N_3$ requires N, 11.26 per cent.).

4-Nitro-2-p-toluoylbenzoic Acid.—4-Nitrophthalic anhydride (7.5 g.) was suspended in toluene (100 c.c.) and to this partially hydrated aluminium chloride (18 g.) was added in small portions during the course of an hour, the flask being shaken continuously all the time. The mixture turned deep green and was then heated on a water-bath at 50-60° for 5 hours. The contents of the flask were then acidified with hydrochloric acid (135 c.c. of 10%) and the excess of toluene distilled off with steam. The crude acid was extracted by hot sodium carbonate solution (100 c.c. of 10%). On acidifying a semi-solid mass (7 g.) was obtained which hardened on keeping. Crystallised from acetic acid, tiny white prisms, m.p. 171°, were obtained. (Found: N, 5.08. $C_{12}H_{11}O_5N$ requires N, 4.91 per cent.).

4-Amino-2-p-toluoylbenzoic Acid.—The reduction of the 4-nitro-acid (4.5 g.) was carried out exactly in the manner employed with the corresponding 3-nitro-acid. Crystallised from water it formed light yellow plates, m.p. 175° (yield, 1.8 g.). (Found: N, 5.67. $C_{15}H_{13}O_3N$ requires N, 5.49 per cent.).

4-Hydroxy-2-p-toluoylbenzoic Acid.—The amino-acid (2 g.) was dissolved in dilute ammonia by warming and dilute hydrochloric acid added until the precipitate first formed dissolved. The solution was cooled to 0° and sodium nitrite (0.6 g.) in water (7 c.c.) gradually added while stirring the mixture mechanically. The solution was then boiled for 15-20 minutes, a little animal charcoal added and filtered hot. An oily precipitate was formed which changed to tiny white crystalline plates on cooling (yield, 1.5 g.). Crystallised from

water it melted at 182-88°. (Found: C, 70·51; H, 4·64. $C_{15}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 70·81; H, 4·89 per cent.).

2-Hydroxy-6-methylanthraquinone.—The hydroxytoluoylbenzoic acid was mixed with boric anhydride and sulphuric acid as in the preparation of 1-hydroxy-6-methylanthraquinone and heated in glycerol-bath at 90-95° for 3 hours. This was then poured into ice when a green mass was obtained which was extracted with hot water. The crude anthraquinone on crystallisation from alcohol gave golden yellow plates (1·5 g.) melting at 278°. (Found: C, 75·49; H, 4·83. $C_{15}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 75·63; H, 4·2 per cent.).

Alkali Fusion of 2-Hydroxy-6-methylanthraquinone.—2-Hydroxy-6-methylanthraquinone (1 g.) was heated in a nickel crucible with potassium hydroxide solution (10 c.c. of 50%) at 185-95° for 1½ hours with addition of sodium arsenate (2 g.) from time to time. The violet coloured melt was extracted with hot water, acidified and filtered. The precipitate of the dihydroxy-methylanthraquinone was extracted by heating with baryta water and the barium-lake decomposed by acid. The process was repeated thrice. The anthraquinone was then dissolved in acetic acid, boiled with the addition of animal charcoal, filtered and the filtrate precipitated with water. The operation was repeated. The precipitate thus obtained was sufficiently pure for crystallisation from glacial acetic acid, when yellow crystals melting at 218-19° were obtained. The m.p. remained unchanged on mixing with 1:2-dihydroxy-6-methylanthraquinone.

2-Acetoxy-6-methylanthraquinone.—This was prepared in the usual way. Light yellow plates, m.p. 145-47° were obtained on crystallisation from alcohol. (Found: C, 72·51; H, 4·48. $C_{17}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 72·86; H, 4·29 per cent.).

2-Methoxy-6-methylanthraquinone.—The hydroxymethylanthraquinone (2 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (6 c.c. of 10%) by warming and dimethyl sulphate (2 c.c.) added, the mixture being shaken well after the addition. Excess of sodium hydroxide solution was then added and the flask heated on the water-bath for an hour. The contents were afterwards boiled with water and filtered. The crude methoxyanthraquinone on crystallisation from alcohol gave yellow needles melting at 177° (yield 1·5 g.). (Found: C, 75·88; H, 4·81. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 76·19; H, 4·76 per cent.).

Dinitro-2-methoxy-6-methylanthraquinone.—2-Methoxy-6-methylanthraquinone (0.5 g.) was mixed with powdered potassium nitrate (0.5 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (3 g.) added. The mixture was heated on a water-bath for 5 hours. The nitro-compound was boiled with water, filtered and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 260-62°. (Found: N, 7.88. $C_{16}H_{10}N_2O_7$ requires N, 8.19 per cent.).

Trimethoxy-6-methylanthraquinone.—The above nitro-compound (0.5 g.) was suspended in absolute methyl alcohol (15 c.c.) and a solution (20 c.c.) of potassium methoxide (prepared by adding 1 g. of potassium to 20 c.c. of absolute methyl alcohol) added. The mixture was heated on the water-bath with reflux condenser for 6 hours and then poured into water (120 c.c.), filtered after boiling and the methoxyanthraquinone obtained was thoroughly dried. The crude product melted at 230-35° and was treated as described below.

Trihydroxy-6-methylanthraquinone.—The substance was intimately mixed with finely powdered aluminium chloride (1.5 g.) and heated to 230° in the course of one hour and then kept at this temperature for half an hour more. When cooled the mixture was transferred to a beaker, using ice-cold water and then boiled with a few c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The residue was collected, dissolved in potassium hydroxide solution (1%), filtered and the filtrate acidified, when thick yellow flakes appeared on boiling. Crystallised from toluene, the orange coloured product melted between 240° and 245°. It gave a beautiful violet coloration in alkaline solution.